

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

PARC T4.1.2.:

Selection of biomarkers of exposure: requirements for inclusion in PARC Aligned Studies

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

Co-funded by
the European Union

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

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1. Introduction

Task 4.1.2 is responsible for the chemical analysis and quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) of human biomonitoring studies in PARC. The work in this task is organised in a stepwise approach that starts with the selection of the biomarkers and matrices and from this, the QA/QC programme is designed and organised. This document explains the process followed for the selection of the biomarkers for the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies, including the criteria applied and the rationale behind the decisions taken, as well as the design of the QA/QC programme.

The process has involved the collaboration of Tasks 2.1 and 9.3 and has been supported by T4.1 and WP4 coleaders. Figure 1 shows the steps taken in the process and further information is provided in the following sections.

Figure 1. Process for the selection of exposure biomarkers and QA/QC programme for the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies.

2. Selection of exposure biomarkers

In February 2023, Laboratoire National de Santé (LNS) – Luxembourg delivered the first list of selected exposure biomarkers for the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies. The work was based on the preparatory phase for PARC done in HBM4EU (3rd HBM4EU prioritisation), followed by the additional prioritisation in PARC considering the alignment with policy regulatory needs (Table 1).

Table 1. Preliminary chemical group selection for the General Survey / Aligned Studies.

Children	Teenagers	Adults
PFAS	PFAS	PFAS
Pesticides	Pesticides	Pesticides
Bisphenols	Bisphenols	Bisphenols
Metals	Arsenic species	Metals
OPFRs	Phthalates & substitutes	Mercury
Phthalates & substitutes		
Mercury		

In a second stage, in collaboration with WP2 (T2.1, “Priority setting”), several independent meetings with ECHA, EFSA and EEA were held to obtain their feedback, which was collected in a comprehensive file to identify their highest priorities ([Document available at T4.1 SharePoint](#); [Document available at ANSES Sharepoint](#)). In parallel, a screening among T4.1.2.1 contributors was done to evaluate the interest and instrumental/technical availability to provide information on the identified biomarkers, as well as to identify the potential multi-residues analytical methods and laboratory capabilities ([in T4.1 SharePoint: Feasibility study for Prioritised substances](#); [in ANSES Sharepoint: Feasibility study for Prioritised substances](#)). As result, a new list of chemical classes / biomarkers (Table 2) was elaborated.

Table 2. Secondary selection of chemical groups for the General Survey.

Children	Teenagers	Adults
	Arsenic species	
Bisphenols	Bisphenols	Bisphenols
Mercury in hair		
Metals (multi-elements) in urine		Metals (multi-elements) in urine
		Metals (multi-elements) in blood
		Pesticides - Glyphosate/AMPA
Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Pyrethroids	Pesticides – Pyrethroids
Pesticides –Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)		Pesticides – Neonicotinoids (Acetamiprid)
Pesticides –Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Pesticides –Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)	Pesticides – Organophosphates (chlorpyrifos)
	PFAS	PFAS
Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	Phthalates & substitutes DINCH	
Cotinine	Cotinine	Cotinine
Creatinine	Creatinine	Creatinine
Specific gravity	Specific gravity	Specific gravity

As an additional source of information that could be considered in the selection of exposure biomarkers, T4.1.1.2. evaluated the national initiatives and interests related to the studies that could potentially take part in the General Survey. Table 3 includes the final proposal of T4.1.2.1

after this prioritisation exercise and delivered in April 2023. The complete overview can be found in this [Excel file](#) available at the T4.1 SharePoint.

Table 3. Biomarkers selected under T4.1.2.1.

Substance group	Chemical class	Matrix	Substance	Biomarker
Metals	Metals	Blood (whole blood)	As, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Al, Li, Mn, Co	As, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, Al, Li, Mn, Co
		Urine	As, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, La, Li, Mn, Co	As and species, Hg, Pb, Cd, Cr, Ni, La, Li, Mn, Co
		Hair	Hg	Hg
Plasticisers	Bisphenols	Urine	TBBPA	Tetrabromo-bisphenol A (TBBPA)
			Bisphenol S	BPS
			Bisphenol B	BPB
			Bisphenol AF	BPAF
			Bisphenol A	BPA
	Phthalates & substitutes	Urine	DMP	MMP
			DEP	MEP
			DnBP (=DBP)	MnBP
			DiBP	MiBP
			BzBP	MBzP
			DEHP	MEHP, 5-oxo-MEHP, 5-OH-MEHP, 5-cx-MEPP, 2-cx-MMHP
			DnOP	MnOP
			DiNP	MiNP, OH-MiNP, cx-MiNP
			DiDP	(MiDP), OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP
			DINCH	MINCH, OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH, oxo-MINCH
			DnPP	MnPeP=MnPP
			DEHTP	MEHTP, 5-Cx-MEPTP, 5OH-MEHTP
			TOTM	1-MEHTM, 2-MEHTM, 4-MEHTM, 5-OH-1-MEHTM, 5-OH-2-MEHTM, 5oxo-1-MEHTM, 5oxo-2-MEHTM, 5cx-1-MEPTM, 5cx-2-MEPTM, 2cx-2-MMHTM, 2cx-1-MMHTM
			DEHA	5-oxo-MEHA, 5-OH-MEHA, 5-cx-MEPA
			Pesticides	Neonicotinoids
Pyrethroids	Urine	Bifenthrin		CIF3CA (=CMFP)
		Cyfluthrin		cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA, 4-F-3-PBA
		(Lambda-) Cyhalothrin		3-PBA, CIF3CA (=CMFP)
		Cypermethrin		3-PBA, cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA
		Deltamethrin		3-PBA, cis-DCCA
		Permethrin		3-PBA, cis-DCCA, trans-DCCA
Organophosphates	Urine	Chlorpyrifos (ethyl and methyl and oxon)		TCPy DEP, DETP (non-specific)
Others	Urine	Glyphosate/AMPA		Glyphosate and AMPA
PFAS	Perfluorinated acids	Blood (serum)		PFBA
			PFBS	PFBS
			PFHxA	PFHxA
			PFHpA	PFHpA
			PFOA	PFOA

Substance group	Chemical class	Matrix	Substance	Biomarker
			PFNA	PFNA
			PFDA	PFDA
			PFUDA	PFUDA
			PFDoDA	PFDoDA
			PFTTrDA	PFTTrDA
			PFTeDA	PFTeDA
			PFHxS	PFHxS
			PFHpS	PFHpS
			PFOS	PFOS
			PFNS	PFNS
			PFDCS	PFDCS
	PFDoS	PFDoS		
	Polyfluorinated precursors	Blood (serum)	PFOSA	PFOSA
			4:2 FTS	4:2 FTS
			6:2 FTS	6:2 FTS
8:2 FTS			8:2 FTS	
			10:2 FTS	10:2 FTS

3. Design of the PARC QA/QC programme

The PARC QA/QC programme is a joint activity of T4.1.2.2 and T9.3 in which the Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) is also participating.

During the first steps of the programme definition, two main approaches were evaluated:

- 1) To apply the same strategy followed in HBM4EU and design a tailor-made programme, taking advantage of the experience acquired.
- 2) To try to link the PARC QA/QC programme to an available commercial proficiency test.

The advantages and difficulties of both alternatives were considered. Based on the success of the tailor-made approach in HBM4EU, this was the first option considered. The Standard Operating Procedures for the organization, control material preparation and testing, etc. are available and could be used with minor adaptations as many groups of substances already present in HBM4EU have been also included for analysis in PARC. However, the situation in PARC is significantly different from the one in HBM4EU and despite the advantages of the experience and the possibility of a total control in the design, serious difficulties were foreseen for this approach (Figure 1).

There were several issues that made this option not feasible in PARC. The main one is the poor funding, an important difficulty already experienced in HBM4EU that would be even worse in PARC due to the lower co-funding rate. This issue was highlighted in the initial stages of the PARC proposal when a request for a 100% funding rate for these activities was made. Secondly, several partners involved in the organisation of the HBM4EU QA/QC Programme are not in PARC, so part of the expertise is lost and it would take considerable efforts to find new expert laboratories experienced with PT/ICI/EQUAS organisation and control material preparation and testing. In addition, the tailor-made option does not allow the possibility of continuing offering the QA/QC programme for HBM in Europe after PARC, and this is a key issue under the perspective of sustainability.

Pros	Cons
Tailor - made QA/QC programme	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☺ Same substances ☺ SOPs available ☺ Experience and lesson learnt 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Lower co-funding ⊗ Some key partners are not involved in PARC ⊗ No continuation of the QA/QC programme after PARC
Use of commercial programmes	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☺ Logistic and structure already set ☺ Experience ☺ Collaborative action, good for the development HBM in Europe ☺ PARC results are comparable with results from outside PARC ☺ Higher number of participants improves statistical evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⊗ Parameters offered ⊗ Range of concentrations ⊗ Timeline

Figure 1. Advantages and limitations of the approaches considered for the PARC QA/QC programme.

In the case of using a commercial programme, we could use their logistics and structure what facilities the implementation, but we would not control the parameters offered, concentration ranges, the schedule of the rounds, and the criteria used for acceptable/questionable/non-acceptable performance.

After considering all the factors, we tried an intermediate solution, to link, among all commercial PT available, the PARC QA/QC programme to the G-EQUAS (German External Quality Assessment Scheme). The G-EQUAS is a proficiency test for human biomonitoring parameters initiated in 1982 organised by IPASUM, the Institute and Outpatient Clinic of Occupational, Social, and Environmental Medicine of the Friedrich – Alexander University in Germany, a key partner in the implementation of the HBM4EU QA/QC programme. After a first discussion with the responsible person of G-EQUAS, Thomas Göen, we confirmed that there was a realistic possibility for adapting the G-EQUAS to PARC’s needs and that the schedule fitted in our plans. This collaboration allows us to start the programme earlier and thus, less experienced laboratories can have more time to develop their methods. Furthermore, since it is an already established exercise, the laboratories can join at any time, and we avoid the problem of having a minimum number of participants for the evaluation of the results of the proficiency test. Furthermore, the transfer of samples within Europe is easier (less problems with customs’ bureaucracy). Strategically this a great opportunity to support the sustainability of HBM in Europe because this can be a first step to establish a continuous QA/QC programme focused on human biomonitoring, independent of project funding, the same philosophy that we followed with the HBM laboratory network.

4. Refinement of the biomarkers list

The list provided by LNS as part of the work done in the 4.1.2.1, the PARC proposal, was carefully revised. In a first step, we cross-checked this list with the following information/data:

- Analyses done in HBM4EU: for comparison purposes and time trends analysis, as well as to know the detection frequency of the target chemicals in the studied populations.
- Comparison with the list of biomarkers analysed worldwide in HBM programmes: the list was compared with the biomarkers analysed in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) of the CDC, the Canadian Health Measures Survey (CHMS), the German Environmental Survey (GerES), the Korean National Environmental Health Survey (KoNEHS), the Japan Environment and Children's Study (JECS) and the Flemish Environment and Health Study (FLEHS).
- Results from the HBM4EU QA/QC: to assess how many laboratories have the capacities to analyse the target biomarkers and the range of concentrations of the qualified laboratories.
- Biomarkers in G-EQUAS: to check the current biomarkers offered and the possibility of including additional biomarkers of interest.

All this information was compiled by ISCIII and shared with the QAWG and Thomas Göen in preparation for a meeting for the refinement of the biomarkers in the PARC proposal (01/06/2023). During the meeting, the list of biomarkers of exposure that are of interest to be investigated in the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies were discussed. Different levels were initially established for the evaluation. In order to avoid the situation we had in HBM4EU in which the study owners were free to select the target biomarkers and this resulted in the fact that for some biomarkers we did not have data from all the countries (Table 4), a minimum compulsory set (initially named “harmonised set”) was defined.

Table 4. Biomarkers offered in the HBM4EU QA/QC programme for the 1st priority list and number of studies analysing them.

		N studies adults (total= 11)	N studies teenagers (total= 11)	N studies children (total= 12)
DINCH	OH-MINCH		9	11
	cx-MINCH		10	12
Phthalates	MEP		10	11
	MBzP		11	10
	MiBP		7	10
	MnBP		10	11
	MCHP		n.a.	n.a.
	MnPeP		n.a.	n.a.
	MEHP		11	10
	5OH-MEHP		11	11
	5oxo-MEHP		11	11
	5cx-MEPP		11	11
	MnOP		n.a.	n.a.
	OH-MiNP		9	10
	cx-MiNP		10	9
	OH-MiDP		8	10
	cx-MiDP		7	7
Bisphenols	BPA	11		
	BPF	10		
	BPS	10		
PFAS	PFPeA		7	
	PFHxA		6	
	PFHpA		8	
	PFOA		8	
	PFNA		8	
	PFDA		8	
	PFUnDA		8	
	PFDoDA		n.a.	
	PFBS		n.a.	
	PFHxS		8	
	PFHpS		7	
	PFOS		n.a.	
HFRs	BDE-47			4
	BDE-153			4
	BDE-209			n.a.
	α-HBCD			n.a.
	γ-HBCD			n.a.
	DP-syn			4
	DP-anti			4
	TBBPA			n.a.
	DBDPE			n.a.
	2,4,6-TBP			n.a.
OPFRs	DPHP			7
	BDCIPP			7
	BCIPP			6
	BCEP			n.a.
PAHs	1-naphthol	7		

		N studies adults (total= 11)	N studies teenagers (total= 11)	N studies children (total= 12)
	2-naphthol	10		
	1,2 DHN	n.a.		
	2-FLUO	7		
	3-FLUO	5		
	9-FLUO	n.a.		
	1-PHEN	7		
	2-PHEN	4		
	3-PHEN	4		
	4-PHEN	8		
	9-PHEN	n.a.		
	1-PYR	9		
	3-BaP	n.a.		
	Cd	U-Cd	8	
B-Cd		n.a.		

n.a.: not analysed

The technical criteria for inclusion in the **PARC Aligned Studies biomarkers list** were:

1. Availability of commercial analytical reference standards of the target substances.
2. Offered in the G-EQUAS or possibility of inclusion in it.

In addition, those included in the minimum compulsory list (initially named “harmonised set”) were those with known or expected high detection frequency (DF>60%) at the LOQ requirement set for the General Survey / Aligned Studies and for which a high percentage of the surveyed laboratories (at least 60%) with experience in a given substance group can analyse the biomarker. The information required for this criterium was extracted from the data collected from the laboratory questionnaire sent by PARC WP9 to update/expand the European network of human biomonitoring (HBM) laboratories.

The usefulness of measuring biomarkers with low detection frequency was discussed as they could provide valuable information about exposure in EU albeit not answering research questions, such as the investigation of exposure determinants or health effects. Another topic discussed was the inclusion of biomarkers that show difficulties or analytical challenges but that could be interesting for generating new data and hypotheses.

As a result, it was agreed to add an additional level/list, the **PARC Discovery scope**, to include these biomarkers. Table 5 shows the levels of biomarkers (and the criteria) established for the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies based on the discussions and agreements in the expert group.

Table 5. Levels of biomarkers defined for the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies.

1. PARC Aligned Studies scope <i>Biomarkers to be measured in the PARC Aligned Studies</i>	2. PARC Discovery scope <i>Optional, interesting exposure biomarkers for new hypothesis generation</i>
Commercial standards must be available	Standards must be available
Covered in the existing G-EQUAS or possibility to include it in the programme	Not (yet) covered by G-EQUAS
<i>For the minimum compulsory set:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Known or expected high detection frequency (>60%) in target population at the LOQ requirement set for the PARC Aligned Study</i> • <i>A high percentage (at least 60%) of the surveyed laboratories with experience in a given substance group should be capable of analysing the biomarker.</i> 	

During the evaluation process, a preliminary list based on three levels was provided to Study Owners with a first overview of the potential biomarkers to be analysed. After two rounds of revision, the final list of biomarkers was defined as shown in table 6.

Table 6. Evaluation of biomarkers to be analysed in the PARC General Survey / Aligned Studies.

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Bisphenols in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 31)								
Bisphenol A (BPA)	Y	Y		Yes	0.57 - 22.3	31	0.02-10	
Bisphenol S (BPS)	Y	Y		Yes	0.82 - 2.20	28	0.02-1	
Bisphenol F (BPF)	Y	Y		Yes	0.95 - 2.07	30	0.02-10	
Bisphenol E (BPE) *			Y			6	0.02-0.5	
Bisphenol AP (BPAP) *			Y			7	0.02-0.5	
Bisphenol AF			Y	Not projected		12	0.02-1	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it is not projected to be included in G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
Bisphenol Z			Y	Not projected		6	0.02-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it is not projected to be included in G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
Bisphenol B			Y	Not projected		7	0.1-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it is not projected to be included in G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
Bisphenol P (BPP) *			Y	Not projected		4	0.1-0.3	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it is not projected to be included in G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
Tetrabromobisphenol A	Excluded					-	-	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope (low level detection) but no labs reported its analysis
Bisphenol S-methacrylate ester (BPS-MAE) *	Excluded					-	-	Originally suggested in Discovery scope but no labs reported its analysis
Pergafast 201*	Excluded					-	-	Originally suggested in Discovery scope but no labs reported its analysis

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Tetrachlorobisphenol A (TCBPA)*	Excluded					-	-	Excluded during our TC and no labs reported its analysis
Phthalates & substitutes in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 28; number of laboratories reporting DINCH metabolites = 17)								
MBzP	Y	Y		Yes	0.7 - 8.6	25	0.005-20	
MiBP	Y	Y		Yes	3.9 - 84.2	23	0.05-20	
MnBP	Y	Y		Yes	3.1 - 57.7	24	0.05-20	
MEHP	Y	Y		Yes	0.5 - 24.2	26	0.05-10	
5OH-MEHP	Y	Y		Yes	3.30 - 97.8	28	0.01-5	
5oxo-MEHP	Y	Y		Yes	1.85 - 72.4	27	0.01-1	
5cx-MEPP	Y	Y		Yes	2.80 - 102	23	0.01-2	
cx-MiNP	Y	Y		Yes	not yet offered	19	0.01-2	The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
MEP	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	21	0.05-20	It has been included in G-EQUAS since round no. 72. It can be included in PARC Aligned Studies scope
OH-MINCH	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	17	0.01-20	The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
cx-MINCH	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	16	0.005-30	The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
oxo-MINCH	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	11	0.01-0.5	The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
OH-MiNP	Y			Yes	not yet offered	15	0.03-1.5	The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
5-cx-MEPTP *	Y			Yes	no data (first run)	6	0.01-0.2	Originally suggested in Discovery scope but if there are standards, it can be moved to PARC Aligned Studies scope: Standard and its deuterium labelled standard are commercially available from Toronto Research Chemicals

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
5OH-MEHTP *	Y			Yes	no data (first run)	6	0.01-0.2	Originally suggested in Discovery scope but If there are standards, it can be moved to PARC Aligned Studies scope: Standard and its deuterium labelled standard are commercially available from Toronto Research Chemicals
Mono-2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl adipate (5OH-MEHA)			Y			2	0.2	Only two labs reported its analysis, maintain in Discovery scope
Mono-5-carboxy-2-ethylpentyl adipate (5cx-MEPA)			Y			2	0.05-0.2	Only two labs reported its analysis, maintain in Discovery scope
MnPeP			Y	Not projected		14	0.04-20	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it cannot be added to G-EQUAS. Restricted/banned phthalate, in Discovery scope to monitor that they are not in use
MnOP			Y	Not projected		16	0.005-20	Restricted/banned phthalate, in Discovery scope to monitor that they are not in use although very low detection frequencies in HBM4EU
MCHP			Y	Not projected		15	0.005-20	Originally suggested to be in PARC Aligned Studies scope but it cannot be added to G-EQUAS, so it should be moved to Discovery scope
OH-MiDP			Y	Not projected		15	0.02-20	It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, so it should be included in Discovery scope. The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)
cx-MiDP			Y	Not projected		9	0.02-1	It cannot be added to G-EQUAS and low % of labs, so it should be included in Discovery scope. The sum of isomers should be reported (as in HBM4EU)

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
MEHTP *	Excluded					1	0.2	Secondary metabolites 5-cx-MEPTP and 5OH-MEHTP included, which are included in G-EQUAS and only one lab reported its analysis
2-cx-MMHP	Excluded					-	-	Excluded by QAWG, considered of little added value as more commonly measured metabolites are already measured
MiNP	Excluded					7	0.15-1.5	Excluded by QAWG, considered of little added value as more commonly measured metabolites are already measured
MiDP	Excluded					4	0.15-0.16	Excluded by QAWG, considered of little added value as 3 more commonly measured metabolites are already measured
MINCH	Excluded					4	0.15-0.2	Excluded by QAWG, considered of little added value as more commonly measured metabolites are already measured
PFAS in serum (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 22)								
PFNA	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	20	0.000012-0.5	
PFDA	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	17	0.00001-0.5	
PFBS	Y	Y		Yes	not yet offered	20	0.01-0.158	
PFHxS	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	20	0.01-0.5	
PFHpS	Y	Y		Yes	no data (first run)	16	0.01-0.5	
PFOA	Y	Y		Yes	0.80 - 48.6	22	0.00007-0.5	
PFOS	Y	Y		Yes	1.34 - 47.6	22	0.00004-1	
4:2 FTSA			Y			4	0.01-0.5	
6:2 FTSA			Y			7	0.023-0.5	
8:2 FTSA			Y			6	0.023-0.5	
9CL-PF3ONS			Y			2	0.009-1	

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
PFHxA			Y	No		19	0.00004-0.5	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope. Discussed by QAWG: very low DF in literature / very low LOQ is needed. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFHpA			Y	No		18	0.00003-0.5	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope. Discussed by QAWG: very low DF in literature / very low LOQ is needed. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFDoDA			Y	No		18	0.000016-0.5	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFUnDA			Y	No		17	0.000012-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFPeA			Y	No		17	0.00004-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFBA			Y	No		18	0.00004-1	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
PFNS			Y	No		2	0.009-0.05	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope, although low DF. Only two labs reported its analysis, and it cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
EtFOSAA			Y	No		8	0.01-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope. Low DF. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope
MeFOSAA			Y	No		8	0.01-0.5	Originally suggested in PARC Aligned Studies scope. Low DF. It cannot be added to G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Adona			Y	No		12	0.01-1	It cannot be included in G-EQUAS and only 54% of labs
GenX			Y	No		11	0.01-10	It cannot be included in G-EQUAS and only 50% of labs
PFDcS	Excluded					-	-	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope, but no labs reported its analysis
PFDoS	Excluded					1	0.009	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope, but only one lab reported its analysis
PFOSA	Excluded					-	-	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope, but no labs reported its analysis
10:2 FTS	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis
F-53	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis
PFTrDA	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis
PFUnDS	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis
PFTrDs	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis
Pesticides-Neonicotinoids in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 10)								
N-desmethyl acetamiprid	Y	Y		Yes	Not yet offered	6	0.1-0.6	Will be included from round 74 G-EQUAS
Acetamiprid	Y	Y		No	Not yet offered	6	0.05-5	Will be included from round 74 G-EQUAS
Imidacloprid	Y	Y		No	Not yet offered	10	0.05-50	Will be included from round 74G-EQUAS
Imidacloprid olefin			Y	No		3	0.1	Originally in PARC Aligned Studies scope but only three labs reported its analysis, it cannot be added in G-EQUAS, moved to Discovery scope

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Imidacloprid 5-hydroxy			Y	No		2	0.1-0.17	Only two labs reported its analysis, it cannot be added in G-EQUAS, keep in Discovery scope
Imidacloprid desnitro	Excluded					-	-	Originally in Discovery scope, but no labs reported its analysis, excluded
Pesticides-Pyrethroids in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 21)								
cis-DBCA	Y	Y		Yes	0.26 - 4.56	14	0.01-2	
cis-DCCA	Y	Y		Yes	0.26 - 4.45	17	0.01-0.07	
trans-DCCA	Y	Y		Yes	0.35 - 6.79	17	0.01-2	
3-PBA	Y	Y		Yes	0.61 - 14.1	21	0.01-0.5	
4-F-3-PBA	Y	Y		Yes	0.26 - 6.12	15	0.01-0.5	
ClF3CA	Y			Yes	0.35 - 2.85	9	0.01-1	
Pesticides-Organophosphates in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 16)								
TCPy	Y	Y		Yes	1.28 - 48.4	16	0.01-1	
DEP	Excluded			Yes	2.16 - 52.8	13	0.02-2	Excluded: i) non-specific biomarker for OPPs, ii) typically requires an additional method, ii) number of OPPs in EU has substantially decreased, iv) for OPPs still in use/around in the EU, more specific biomarkers exist, although non-specific biomarkers give better detection frequencies
DETP	Excluded			Yes	2.33 - 91.1	14	0.02-1	Excluded: i) non-specific biomarker for OPPs, ii) typically requires an additional method, ii) number of OPPs in EU has substantially decreased, iv) for OPPs still in use/around in the EU, more specific biomarkers exist, although non-specific biomarkers give better detection frequencies
Pesticides-Others in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 19)								
Glyphosate	Y	Y		Yes	0.22 - 3.73	19	0.01-500	
AMPA	Y	Y		Yes	not yet offered	17	0.01-0.5	

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Metals in whole blood (except Se, see below) (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 38)								
Hg	Y	Y		Yes	0.26 - 1.41	29	0.007-4; (0.05-2 ng/g)	
Pb	Y	Y		Yes	4.49 -60.2	38	0.025-500; (0.05-5 ng/g)	
Cd	Y	Y		Yes	0.12 - 1.14	38	0.002-2; (0.03-3 ng/g)	
Cr	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	1.40 - 9.80	22	0.028-5; (0.05-0.6 ng/g)	Occupational range
Mn	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	5.90 - 32	23	0.072-5.2; (0.05-1 ng/g)	Occupational range
Co	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	1.37 -45.4	20	0.016-2; (0.008-0.09 ng/g)	Occupational range
Se	Y			<i>In plasma</i>		4	0.1-5; (0.28 ng/g)	<i>Measurement of Se is done in serum or in plasma. The G-EQUAS is in plasma</i>
As	Excluded			No		-	-	Excluded by QAWG, diagnostic validity unclear, and no labs reported its analysis
Ni	Excluded			Yes (occup. range material)	2.36 - 28.5	-	-	Excluded by QAWG, not common in HBM programmes, and no labs reported its analysis
Al	Excluded			No		-	-	Excluded by QAWG, difficult to avoid contamination, including sampling, not advisable for general survey, and no labs reported its analysis
Li	Excluded			No		-	-	Excluded by QAWG, not common in HBM programmes, and no labs reported its analysis
Metals in urine (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 42)								
Total As	Y	Y		Yes	11.2 - 127	34	0.02-5.2; (0.17 ng/g)	
As (III)	Y	Y		Yes	0.16 - 0.89	12	0.05-1.3	

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
As (V)	Y	Y		Yes	0.23 - 1.15	12	0.05-0.8	
MMA	Y	Y		Yes	0.44 - 2.57	12	0.05-0.7	
DMA	Y	Y		Yes	1.61 - 25.8	12	0.05-0.6	
Arsenobetaine	Y	Y		Yes	2.68 -127	9	0.05-0.5	
Cd	Y	Y		Yes	0.10 - 1.06	40	0.002-1.5	
Hg	Y			Yes	0.10 -1.16	30	0.01-2	
Pb	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	3.26 - 68.2	42	0.003-50; (0.081 ng/g)	Occupational range
Cr	Y			Yes	0.25 - 1.17	31	0.02-5	
Ni	Y			Yes	0.56 - 6.46	16	0.04-3.5	
Al	Y			Yes (mix of environmental and occup. range material)	9.79 - 69.5	6	0.1-2.14	Occupational range
Li	Y			Yes (mix of environmental and occup. range material)	16.6 - 301	3	0.022-0.224	Occupational range
Mn	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	1.90 - 33.6	30	0.01-5; (0.036 ng/g)	Occupational range
Co	Y			Yes (occup. range material)	2.30 - 100	29	0.002-2; (0.01 ng/g)	Occupational range
Pt	Y			Yes		3	0.002-0.008	
Cu	Y			Yes		7	0.24-10.3	
Sr	Y			Yes		13	0.025-10	

Biomarker	PARC Aligned Studies scope		PARC Discovery scope	Possibility to be included in the future in G-EQUAS (or adapt the range)	Concentration range in G-EQUAS (last 5 years) (µg/L)	Num. Labs #	Reported LOQ (µg/L)	Comments
	Complete set	Minimum compulsory set						
Zn	Y			Yes		5	3.5-30	
Mo	Y			Yes		24	0.009-12.5; (0.35 ng/g)	
Sn	Y			Yes		18	0.01-2	
Ca	Excluded			Yes		-	-	No labs reported its analysis
Mercury in hair (total number of laboratories reporting analysis in HBM laboratory network = 13)								
Total Hg	Y	Y				13	0.012-28 ng/g	PT organised by ISCIII

number of laboratories reporting experience in this analysis in the laboratory questionnaire sent by PARC WP9, for each group of substances the total number of laboratories reporting analysis in the HBM laboratory network is provided in the respective row.

*biomarker interesting for WP5

5. Final list

Biomarkers and other parameters to be analysed in PARC Aligned Studies	Optional biomarkers to analyse in PARC for Discovery scope
Bisphenols in urine	
Bisphenol A (BPA)*, Bisphenol S (BPS)*, Bisphenol F (BPF)*	Bisphenol E (BPE), Bisphenol AP (BPAP), Bisphenol AF, Bisphenol Z, Bisphenol B, Bisphenol P (BPP),
Phthalates & substitutes in urine	
MBzP*, MiBP*, MnBP*, MEHP*, 5OH-MEHP*, 5oxo-MEHP*, 5cx-MEPP*, cx-MiNP*, MEP*, OH-MINCH*, cx-MINCH*, oxo-MINCH*, OH-MiNP, 5-cx-MEPTP, 5OH-MEHTP	Mono-2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl adipate (5OH-MEHA), Mono-5-carboxy-2-ethylpentyl adipate (5cx-MEPA), MnPeP, MnOP, MCHP, OH-MiDP, cx-MiDP,
PFAS in serum	
PFNA*, PFDA*, PFBS*, PFHxS*, PFHpS*, PFOA*, PFOS*	4:2 FTSA, 6:2 FTSA, 8:2 FTSA, 9CL-PF3ONS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFDoDA, PFUnDA, PFPeA, PFBA, PFNS, EtFOSAA, MeFOSAA, Adona, GenX
Pesticides-Neonicotinoids in urine	
N-desmethyl acetamiprid*, Acetamiprid*, Imidacloprid*	Imidacloprid olefin, Imidacloprid 5-hydroxy
Pesticides-Pyrethroids in urine	
cis-DBCA*, cis-DCCA*, trans-DCCA*, 3-PBA*, 4-F-3-PBA*, ClF3CA	
Pesticides-Organophosphates in urine	
TCPy*	
Pesticides-Others in urine	
Glyphosate*, AMPA*	
Metals in whole blood	
Hg*, Pb*, Cd*, Cr, Mn, Co, Se (in plasma)	
Metals in urine	
Total As*, As (III)*, As (V)*, MMA*, DMA*, Arsenobetaine*, Cd*, Hg, Pb, Cr, Ni, AL, Li, Mn, Co, Pt, Cu, Sr, Zn, Mo, Sn	
Metals in hair	
Total Hg*	
Cotinine	
Creatinine	
Specific gravity	

*harmonised set = minimum compulsory set to be measured to receive PARC funding

6. Remarks

- For the selection, the possibility of measuring different metabolites in the same method as well as the budgetary issues were considered.
- **Harmonisation issues.** For phthalates and DINCH, as in HBM4EU, special instructions will be given to all the laboratories regarding the determination of the biomarkers of the long-chain phthalates and DINCH. This includes the use of specified transition in the LC-MS/MS and the use of sufficiently wide acquisition window to ensure that all isomer peaks for these biomarkers are included in the measurement.
- For the **PFAS selection**, the inclusion of new PFAS as well as those in the Commission recommendation on the monitoring of PFAS in food (2022/1431) and the EU Directive on the quality of water intended for human consumption (2020/2184), was considered.
- For the **analysis of PFAS**, the use of serum or plasma as matrix was discussed, the final recommendation is the use of serum in the PARC Aligned Studies. This has been included in the Best Practice Documents. Blood collection tubes that contain a separating gel often used to obtain blood serum should be avoided as the gel separators are a potential source of certain contaminants like PFAS. If used, it must be ensured that the sampling material is free of contamination (the tubes should be tested). This must be indicated in the sampling procedure documents. For the quality assurance of PFAS analysis in serum the G-EQUAS PFAS in plasma is valid (as indicated by the G-EQUAS coordinators and the PARC QAWG). The recommendation is that laboratories report both linear PFAS (as in G-EQUAS) and total PFAS.
- **Mercury in hair.** Since G-EQUAS does not cover this biomarker/matrix, ISCIII will organise the PT based on their experience acquired during the organization of COPHES/DEMOCOPHES ICI/EQUAS for total mercury in hair. They will follow the common instructions on QA/QC provided from T9.3 (joint activities-harmonisation).
- **Creatinine measures.** Some laboratories already participate in PTs for creatinine, or they outsource to contract laboratories that perform it as routine analysis and are accredited. Information has been collected by means of the laboratory questionnaire sent by PARC WP9. From a total of 108 laboratories, 54 analyse routinely creatinine and 30 of these participate regularly in PTs. Most of these (n=16) participate in G-EQUAS. Other programmes reported are: Biologie Prospective France, BIO-RAD, CSCQ, ERNDIM, HBM4EU, INSTAND, LabQuality, Probioqual, RfB, RIQAS Human Urine EQA/G-EQUAS, Sciensano, SEKK (Czech EQA), and SEQC. This information will be shared with T9.3 and based on that, they will make a recommendation. The G-EQUAS would be the option for those laboratories that do not participate in PTs.